

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDIES ON DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF NYLON 6/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES

S.N. Song, Y. Chen, Z.C. Su, C.G. Quan, V.B.C. Tan*

Department of Mechanical Engineering, National University of Singapore
9 Engineering Drive 1, Singapore, 117576

*Corresponding author (mpetanbc@nus.edu.sg)

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Abstract

A hierarchical multiscale model of a 3D representative volume element (RVE) for nylon 6/clay nanocomposites was introduced to study its constitutive properties and damage behavior. The model was composed of a nylon 6 matrix with embedded silicate layers. A gallery inter-layer was inserted between the intercalated silicate layers and an interphase layer was added around the silicate layers to mimic actual nylon 6/clay nanocomposites. In order to characterize the mechanical behavior of the nanocomposites, the material properties of its constituents need to be determined. Nylon 6 or the so-called polyamide 6 is a typical thermoplastic material. Thermoplastic materials could undergo quite large deformation before rupture. A progressive damage criterion which takes into account triaxiality effects on damage initiation was applied to simulate the pure nylon 6. Experimental work on tensile testing of pre-notched bars was carried out to obtain the damage parameters for the nylon 6. The damage process of the gallery layer and the interphase layer was governed by a traction-separation law which was obtained by performing molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. The silicate layers are assumed to be only linear elastic without damage. The constitutive relationship and damage patterns of the numerical model of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites were examined by explicit FEM under the quasi-static uniaxial stress tension loading. The effect of the strength of the gallery layer and the interphase layer on the constitutive relationship was also studied.

1 Introduction

Polymer nanocomposites are a novel class of materials where nanometer-sized fillers are introduced into a distinct polymer matrix. In recent years, polymer nanocomposites have drawn great attention both in industry and academia. A polymer nanocomposites system generally contains two

material phases—the polymer matrix and nanometer-sized fillers. The polymer matrix could be either thermoplastic polymer or thermoset polymer. According to their shape, nanometer-sized fillers can be divided into dot-like, tube-like and plate-like. Examples for these three types of nanometer-sized fillers are nano-silica, nano-tube and nano-clay respectively. Among various polymer nanocomposites, the polymer/clay nanocomposites have been widely used in automotive structures, aircrafts, infrastructure, etc. The nano-clay is a general term for layered silicate minerals with high stiffness and strength. The aspect ratio of mono silicate platelet usually is about 100-1000 [1-3]. These stacked silicate layers will separate to form either intercalated state or exfoliated state when they are blending with the polymer matrix. Dispersion of low weight fraction (<5%) of these silicate layers in the polymer matrix will lead to significant improvements in mechanical, thermal and barrier properties compared with the traditional polymers.

Nano-clay reinforced nylon 6 nanocomposites were first prepared by the Toyota research group [4, 5]. Since then, the preparation and their mechanical behavior have been extensively studied. It has been well documented that the Young's modulus and the yield stress could be improved with the incorporation of layered silicates. However, the damage behavior of these nylon 6/clay nanocomposites has yet to be well characterized. A good understanding of the damage behavior of nanocomposites is particularly important for structural design and other practical applications. Experiments have been carried out to observe the damage and fracture mechanisms of polymer nanocomposites. Examples of experimental studies on nylon 6/clay nanocomposites were reported in [6, 7]. However, now it is still difficult and expensive to accurately analyse the micromechanics of the polymer nanocomposites through experiments due to the nanometer-sized reinforcements. Besides,

analytical approaches, such as effective clay models, are usually considered to study the mechanical behaviors of polymer/clay nanocomposites [8, 9]. However, these effective clay models could not explicitly represent the constituents of the clay particle. Therefore, the analytical models could not well resolve damage problems of polymer/clay nanocomposites with complex microstructure.

Computational micromechanics is emerging as a powerful tool to study the mechanical behavior of heterogeneous materials including nanocomposites. In the polymer/clay nanocomposites, the relationship between the hierarchical structure and mechanical properties can be characterized by the corresponding hierarchical multiscale modeling method, covering computational methods ranging from the atomic length scale to the continuum scale [10]. Simulations at the atomic length scale contain Quantum Mechanics (QM), Monte Carlo (MC) and Molecular Dynamics (MD). These simulations could take the molecular interaction into consideration. However, the applications of these simulations are limited by prohibitive computational time when the model comprises too many atoms. At this stage, traditional finite element method (FEM) and continuum mechanics could be a more practical choice. In the hierarchical multiscale modeling method, material properties of the constituents of the nanocomposites obtained from a lower scale can be input into a model of larger length scale for further calculation. In this study the computational methods at lower scale and continuum scale respectively refer to MD simulations and FEM.

The structure of this manuscript is arranged as follows. Firstly, a 3D RVE which mimics the actual nylon 6/clay nanocomposites model is introduced. Secondly, the materials properties of the constituents of the nylon 6/clay nanocomposites were determined by using experimental approaches or MD simulations. The material properties of nylon 6 were obtained by carrying out tensile test on pre-notched bars. The damage property of nylon 6 is described by a progressive ductile damage criterion which has been integrated in the commercial FEM codes, Abaqus. The material properties of the gallery layer and interphase layer were obtained from MD simulations. These properties are expressed by a traction-separation law which has also been integrated in Abaqus. Then these material properties were imported into the 3D RVE model. Lastly, the macroscopic response of the RVE model to quasi-static uniaxial stress loading was solved by explicit

FEM to assess damage behavior of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites. Effects of strength of the gallery layer and the interphase layer on the constitutive relationship of nylon 6/clay model were also studied.

2 Experimental work and Damage criteria

2.1 Clay model and RVE model

It is known that fracture is strongly related to local inhomogeneities in composite materials. The presence of nano-clay may produce discontinuities at nano and micro scales due to its thickness, width and agglomerates. Establishing a computational model that could describe the microstructure of actual polymer/clay nanocomposites is a fundamental task for a reliable prediction of such new systems. In terms of enhancement of mechanical properties, complete exfoliation of clay platelets is desired but never achieved for polymer/clay nanocomposites. For nylon 6/clay nanocomposites with highly exfoliated but intercalated clay platelets, nylon 6 molecules will penetrate between stacked silicate layers to form a gallery layer during the manufacturing process. The interphase layer is represented by one layer between the silicate platelet and the nylon 6 matrix having distinct properties from matrix due to the chemical reaction between the silicate layers and the nylon 6 matrix. The gallery layer, interphase layer and silicate layer collectively form the clay particles as shown in Fig.1.a. In this study, the nano-clay was assumed to be a perfectly round and flat particle for simplicity. The number of silicate layers per nanoparticle was set to be 2 to represent the highly exfoliated but intercalated state. The gallery layer, the interphase layer and silicate layers have the same diameter, $d_g = d_i = d_s = 208\text{nm}$. The thicknesses of the gallery layer, interphase layer and silicate layer are $h_g = 2.82\text{nm}$, $h_i = 6\text{nm}$, and $h_s = 0.95\text{nm}$ respectively based on experimental observations[1-3]. The 3D RVE model comprising four constituents - the matrix, the silicate layer, the gallery layer and the interphase layer - was generated using in-house C++ and python algorithms. In each RVE model, 35 clay particles are randomly and periodically distributed in the cubic matrix. RVE models of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites with 1%, 2.5% and 5% weight fractions of nano-clay were generated for analysis. For each weight fraction, nine models with different resolutions were generated and used in the computations to obtain an average of the predicted properties. The RVE model with 2.5% weight fraction of nano-clay is shown in Fig.1.b. Due to the

complexity of the local geometry, the matrix and silicate layers were meshed with the tetrahedron element - C3D4 elements. The gallery layer and the interphase layer were meshed with 3D cohesive element - COH3D8 elements. In the section 2.2 and 2.3, the determination of material properties of nylon 6 and the gallery layer as well as the interphase layer is discussed.

2.2 Experimental work and Progressive damage criterion for nylon 6

The nylon 6 matrix was assumed to behave as an isotropic solid. Its plasticity was governed by an isotropic plasticity model. Its failure was governed by a progressive damage criterion, given by,

$$W_d = \int_0^{\bar{\varepsilon}_f} \frac{d\bar{\varepsilon}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_f(\eta)} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where, W_d is a state variable, η is the triaxiality which is defined as $\eta = \sigma_m / \sigma_{eq}$, σ_m is the mean stress, as $\sigma_m = (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3) / 3$ and the equivalent stress σ_{eq} is defined as the Mises stress, as $\sigma_{eq} = \sqrt{1/2 [(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2]}$, σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_3 are the principle stress. $\bar{\varepsilon}_f$ is the effective plastic strain at onset of damage. It is a function of triaxiality and strain rate. For the sake of simplicity, in this study $\bar{\varepsilon}_f$ is assumed to be strain rate independent. In the numerical process, W_d is a state variable that increases monotonically with plastic deformation. At each increment during the analysis the incremental increase in W_d is computed as:

$$\Delta W_d = \frac{\Delta \bar{\varepsilon}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_f(\eta)} \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

When $W_d = 1$, it indicates that progressive damage initiation has occurred. In order to build the $\bar{\varepsilon}_f - \eta$ relationship, some experimental work must be carried out. Hooputra et al. [11] have presented for generating different stress triaxiality, the uniaxial tensile test, the biaxial tensile test and the three point bending test should be done. Mae [12] also studied the material ductility of PP/EPR/talc composite with butterfly specimens which can generate wide range of stress triaxiality. However, these experiments are difficult to perform or need special consideration for the clamp design. In order to simplify the situation, the pre-notched bars method was adopted in this study. The pioneering work was performed by Bridgeman [13] who presented analytical solutions for the $\bar{\varepsilon}_f - \eta$ relationship. This solution is based on

the analysis of pre-notched bars, as shown in Fig.2, which can generate different stress triaxiality right at the notched region when the specimens are subjected to uniaxial tensile test. Earl et al. [14] and Bruning et al. [15] have respectively modified the Bridgman analysis. Bao et al. [16, 17] have systematically studied the $\bar{\varepsilon}_f - \eta$ relationship of metal materials through both experimental and numerical approaches with pre-notched bars. Solid polymers have also been studied through this approach [18, 19]. According to Bridgman analysis, the value of the triaxiality and the equivalent plastic strain at onset of fracture of pre-notched bars can be expressed as:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{3} + \ln \left(\frac{r_0}{2R} + 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_f = 2 \ln \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right) \quad (4)$$

where, r is the radius of the minimum cross-section and R is the radius of the circumferential notch, r_0 is the initial value of r .

In this study, a series of circumferentially blunt-notched bars were also used to generate different triaxial stress state, as shown in Fig.2. The uniaxial tensile test was performed. From Fig.3, it can be seen that the nylon 6 specimen is clamped by Instron tensile testing machine. Strain gages, an extensometer and a camera were used to record the deformation of the specimens during the loading process. Nylon 6 has a very large plastic deformation before the onset of damage and may vary significantly due to manufacturing or other factors. As a result, it is very difficult to obtain an accurate value of $\bar{\varepsilon}_f$. However, it is believed that Equ.3 and Equ.4 could ensure reasonable results. Besides, the triaxiality may be very high when different materials are modeled together in the RVE model. However, it is almost impossible to do a test with very high triaxiality state. In fact, it is reasonable to assume a cut off value for $\bar{\varepsilon}_f$ when the triaxiality is very large, as in this case the ductile damage theory is not valid any more. At the same time, it is assumed that nylon 6 will not damage when the triaxiality is negative (corresponding to compression test) which is based on experimental work [20]. The $\bar{\varepsilon}_f - \eta$ relationship is plotted in Fig. 4. For the fracture evolution, Hillerborg's [21] fracture energy proposal was adopted to allay the mesh sensitivity problem. As complete fracture

occurs quickly after fracture initiation, the fracture energy G was set to be a trivial value.

2.3 Traction-separation law

The damage of the gallery layer mimics clay splitting and the fracture of interphase layer denotes debonding between the clay and matrix in the nylon 6/clay nanocomposites. The damage process of these two layers was governed by a traction-separation law or the so-called cohesive zone model. The traction-separation law is based on the assumption that the elements are characterized by progressive degradation of the material stiffness. The traction-separation law is often applied for delamination modeling. Examples of applying the cohesive zone model to delamination modeling are reported in [22-24]. It should be noted that the traction-separation law is initially designed for interfaces with negligible thickness. Since the gallery layer and interface layer have relatively large aspect ratio, it is reasonable to apply the traction-separation law to these two interfaces.

The damage process requires accurate characterization of the interfacial or bonded material. However, in the nylon 6/clay nanocomposites, the deformation procedures of the gallery layer and the interphase layer are quite hard to determine through experimental measurements. In this condition, followed the work by Chen et al. [25] MD simulations were performed to estimate the traction-separation law for the gallery layer and the interphase layer. Detailed procedures for performing MD simulations can be found in [25].

The corresponding traction-separation laws obtained from MD simulations are presented in Fig.5 and the degradation parts are expressed by fitting curves as:

$$\sigma_{coh}^g = 228\sigma^c (1+u)^{-2.4} \quad (5)$$

For the interphase layer,

$$\sigma_{coh}^i = 250\sigma^c (1+u)^{-2.3} \quad (6)$$

where, σ_{coh}^g , σ_{coh}^i are the cohesive stress of the gallery layer and the interphase layer corresponding to the effective displacement u . The tensile strength, denoted as σ^c , of the gallery layer and the interphase layer is 146MPa and 135MPa respectively according to the MD simulations. The elastic modulus of gallery layer and interphase layer were defined as the ratio of the MD cohesive strength σ^c to the corresponding strain prior to damage initiation. Values of $E_{coh}^g = 2.06\text{GPa}$ and $E_{coh}^i = 2.71\text{GPa}$ were obtained. The most important

two parameters for a traction-separation law are the cohesive strength and fracture toughness. In this study, these two parameters are coupled. When study the influence of gallery/interphase strength, the shape of the traction-separation law would be unchanged.

For prediction of damage initiation, a stress-based quadratic criterion is selected. It can be written as:

$$\left(t_n / \sigma_n^c\right)^2 + \left(t_s / \sigma_s^c\right)^2 + \left(t_t / \sigma_t^c\right)^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

where, t_n is the nominal traction stress component along normal direction, t_s , t_t , represent the two shear tractions. σ_n^c , σ_s^c , and σ_t^c are the cohesive strengths at which interface failure takes place. In this study, the cohesive strengths are assumed to be equal in all directions. For modeling damage evolution, a damage variable D is specified as a function of the effective displacement.

2.4 Dynamic explicit formulation

Traditionally, the implicit FEM method often fails when material instabilities are involved that would lead to localized failure problems. Nevertheless, finite element codes based on dynamic explicit formulation are favored for solving incremental fracture of materials although implicit codes yield more accurate results for quasi-static problem. The dynamic explicit method also has other advantages compared with the implicit method, i.e., they have low memory requirement.

Many researchers have used dynamic explicit finite element method to study the fracture mechanisms of composite under quasi-static loading. Zhang et al. [26] used the explicit FEM to study fracture mechanism of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites which were subjected to transverse loading. Fan et al. [27] analyzed the fracture mechanics of hydroxyapatite (HA) reinforced polyetheretherketone (PEEK) by implementing the explicit FEM. Siad et al. [28] studied the softening behavior of porous ductile solids through explicit FEM codes. In this proposal, the dynamic explicit FEM was implemented to study the constitutive relationship and damage behavior of nanocomposites subjected to quasi-static uniaxial stress tensile loading.

Dynamic explicit finite element formulation has been reported by many authors and can be reviewed in [29, 30]. The general form of the principle of virtual work is described as follows:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \varepsilon_{ij} \sigma_{ij} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{u}_i \delta u_i d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} b_i \delta u_i d\Omega - \int_S t_i \delta u_i d\Omega = 0 \quad (8)$$

Where \mathbf{u} and $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$ represent the displacement and accelerate vectors, ρ denotes mass density, \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{t} are the body and surface force vectors. $\delta \mathbf{u}$ and $\delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ denote the virtual displacement and virtual strain. Ω and S denote the volume and surface which are under study. The above equation contains terms for internal work, inertia work, work done by the body force, and work done by the surface force. By the discretions of the model with finite element mesh, introducing material behavior model, and incorporating the element shape function and dynamics of the body, the equilibrium formulation of the above equation can be expressed as:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_t = \mathbf{M}^{-1} (\mathbf{P}_t - \mathbf{I}_t) \quad (9)$$

Where \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix, \mathbf{P} is the applied force vector and \mathbf{I} is the internal force vector. A lumped mass is used because its inverse is not needed and the solution can be directly obtained by solving uncoupled linear equations. Therefore, the explicit procedures required no iterations and no tangent stiffness matrix. The equation of motion at the time $t + \Delta t$ can be obtained by integrating over time by using Equ.9 together with the central difference method:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_t = (\mathbf{u}_{t-\Delta t} - 2\mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{u}_{t+\Delta t}) / \Delta t^2 \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}_t = (\mathbf{u}_{t+\Delta t} - \mathbf{u}_{t-\Delta t}) / 2\Delta t \quad (11)$$

and the initial condition is given as:

$$\mathbf{u}_{-\Delta t} = \mathbf{u}_0 - \Delta t \dot{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_0 \Delta t^2 / 2 \quad (12)$$

The explicit procedure integrates through time by using many small time increments. The central-difference operator is conditionally stable. The stability limit is approximated to be:

$$\Delta t \approx \frac{L_{\min}}{c_d} \quad (13)$$

where, L_{\min} is the smallest element dimension in the FE model and c_d is the dilatational wave speed which can be written as:

$$c_d = \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\lambda} + 2\hat{\mu}}{\rho}} \quad (14)$$

Here, ρ is the density of the material. In an isotropic and elastic material the effective lame's constants can be defined in terms of Young's modulus, E and Possion's ratio ν by $\hat{\lambda} = E\nu / (1+\nu)(1-2\nu)$ and $\hat{\mu} = E / 2(1+\nu)$. Combining the Equ.13 and Equ.14, we can obtain:

$$\Delta t \approx \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\hat{\lambda} + 2\hat{\mu}}} \quad (15)$$

In the Abaqus explicit solver, as can be seen from Equ.15 the computational incremental time can be increased by mass scaling. In our model, since the elastic stiffness of silicate layer is much higher than that of the gallery layer, the interphase layer and the nylon 6, mass scaling is used for silicate layer. The kinetic energy should be checked at the end of the simulation to ensure that the kinetic energy does not exceed a small fraction of the total strain energy (internal energy).

2.5 Boundary conditions and homogenization method

Simulation of the RVE under uniaxial stress was carried out and compared with actual experimental results. The displacement boundary condition was applied to the surface nodes of the meshed RVE. Denoting the dimensions of the generated RVE model are L_x , L_y and L_z , the displacement boundary conditions can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} u(0, y, z) &= 0, \\ v(x, 0, z) &= 0, \\ w(x, y, 0) &= 0, \\ v(x, L_y, z) &= \delta_y \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where, δ_y is the prescribed displacement for uniaxial loading along the Y axis; δ_x and δ_z are computed from the condition that the average stress on the surfaces $x = L_x$, $x = 0$, $z = L_z$ and $z = 0$ are equal to zero, as:

$$\int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} \sigma_x(L_x, y, z) dydz = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} \sigma_x(0, y, z) dydz = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \sigma_z(x, y, L_z) dx dy = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \sigma_z(x, y, 0) dx dy = 0 \quad (20)$$

where, $\sigma_x(L_x, y, z)$, $\sigma_x(0, y, z)$ and $\sigma_z(x, y, L_z)$, $\sigma_z(x, y, 0)$ are the stress distribution acting on the surface $x = L_x$, $x = 0$, $z = L_z$ and $z = 0$. These zero resultant force conditions were enforced by multipoint constraint equations.

Homogenized variables at the macroscopic scale are obtained by volume averaging of variables in the RVE. The macroscopic nominal stress $\langle \sigma \rangle$ and strain $\langle \varepsilon \rangle$ can be calculated from [31],

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \frac{1}{|\Omega_m|} \int_{\Omega_m} \sigma_m d\Omega \quad (21)$$

$$\langle \varepsilon \rangle = \frac{1}{|\Omega_m|} \int_{\Omega_m} \varepsilon_m d\Omega \quad (22)$$

Where, σ_m and ε_m are microscopic nominal stress and strain vectors. Ω_m is the volume of the RVE. For this specific problem, the macroscopic nominal stress and strain can be obtained by:

$$\langle \sigma \rangle_y = \frac{f_{R,y}}{L_x \times L_z} \quad (23)$$

$$\langle \varepsilon \rangle_y = \frac{\delta_y}{L_y} \quad (24)$$

where, $f_{R,y}$ is the reaction force on the top surface.

3 Results

The response of the RVE model to quasi-static uniaxial stress loading was solved by explicit FEM. The elastic stiffness of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites has been well documented. However, experimental data for constitutive relationship of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites often varies over a large range due to different manufacturing techniques and environment conditions, i.e., humidity. Prior to the comparison of numerical predictions with the experimental data for constitutive relationship, experimental results for the elastic modulus were used for benchmarking. 35 clay particles were randomly and periodically inserted in each RVE model which is considered to ensure that the RVE is large enough to be statistically representative of the nanocomposites. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the silicate layer are 400GPa and 0.16. It can be seen from Fig. 6 the elastic modulus obtained from the numerical prediction are close to the experimental data [7]. The predicted elastic modulus increases with clay content, suggesting that the elastic modulus of the nanocomposites will be enhanced by the addition of nanoclay particle.

3.1 Damage analysis

As presented in Fig.7, the predicted constitutive relationship of the nylon 6/clay model with 2.5% weight fraction of nano-clay was observed to be in good agreement with experimental data [7]. The fracture patterns of this RVE model were shown in

Fig.8. In the Fig.8, SDEG means stiffness degradation factor and the cohesive element is regard as totally damaged and would be deleted when this value reaches 1. When subjected to a uniaxial load, the interphase layer goes into damage firstly. After the interphase has been removed, the formed void will lead to increase the triaxiality for the nearby polymer matrix, which will accelerate the development of this area of polymer matrix damage. Upon further loading, the microcracks would then propagate into the matrix and finally form a macrocrack. The numerical model can successfully reflect the fracture patterns observed in [7].

3.2 Effect of interphase and gallery strength

In this section, the nanocomposites properties with 2.5% weight fraction of nano-clay as a function of the gallery and the interphase strength are presented. The tensile strength of the gallery layer and interphase layers are equal to 135MPa and 146MPa respectively according to the MD simulation. However, the actual cohesive strength is expected to be equal or lower than the tensile strength obtained from MD simulations due to the presence of defects. The cohesive strength is scaled by a factor, K_g or K_i

($0 < K_g \leq 1$, $0 < K_i \leq 1$) to account for this. When changing these two defect factors, they are assumed to be equal to each other. As can be seen from Fig.9, the elastic modulus of nanocomposites will not be affected significantly. However, the damage stage of the nanocomposites will occur earlier as cohesive strength decreases. It means that microcracks are easily formed due to the weaker gallery and interphase strength. If the clay particles are well distributed into the epoxy matrix during the manufacturing process, i.e., no agglomeration of clay particles, the effects of strength of the gallery layer and the interphase layer could explain why the experimental data for the constitutive relationship of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites shows a large variation.

4 Conclusion

The constitutive relationship and the damage behavior of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites were studied by a hierarchical multiscale modeling method implemented with a 3D RVE model and explicit FEM. The predicted results of constitutive relationship and fracture patterns are close to the experimental data reported in literature. It suggests that this method could be successfully applied to study nylon 6/clay nanocomposites and possibly

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDIES ON DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF NYLON 6/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES

other polymer/clay nanocomposites. The strength of the gallery layer and the interphase layer will significantly affect the strength of the nylon 6/clay nanocomposites, which could explain why the constitutive relationship of nanocomposites often shows a much large variation in the experiments than elastic properties.

Fig.1. (a) Schematic view of nano-clay particle (b) RVE model of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites.

Fig.2. Test specimens for generating different stress triaxiality. The specimens have the same diameter (4 mm) at the minimum cross section. From left to right R= 1mm, 2mm, 4mm, 8mm, smooth.

Fig.3. Experimental set up for tensile test.

Fig.4. Fracture locus of nylon 6. Experiments vs. curve fitting.

Fig.5. Traction-separation law for the gallery layer and the interphase layer.

Fig.6. Elastic modulus of nylon 6/clay nanocomposites with various weight fraction of nano-clay.

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDIES ON DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF NYLON 6/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES

Fig.7. Stress-strain curves of nylon/clay nanocomposites with 2.5% weight fraction of nano-clay.

Fig.8. Macrocrack formed by the coalescence of interphase debonding and matrix damage

Fig.9. Effect of strength of the interphase layer and the gallery layer.

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EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDIES ON DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF NYLON 6/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES

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